

RELISE

*E-BRANDING DIGITAL: AN ANALYSIS OF THE INSTAGRAM POSTS OF THE
COMPANY IFOOD¹*

**E-BRANDING DIGITAL: UMA ANÁLISE DAS POSTAGENS NO INSTAGRAM
DA EMPRESA IFOOD**

Ionara Diniz²

Raissa Barbosa³

Vinicius de Lima Torres Leite⁴

ABSTRACT

This study examines the e-branding strategies employed by iFood, through a case study of its posts on Instagram during the period from January 5th to April 16th, 2024. Using qualitative methodology and content analysis, it investigates the main characteristics of iFood's branding on the platform. The results reveal that iFood adopts a strategic approach on Instagram, aiming to build a strong and relevant brand for its target audience. The company uses several resources, such as storytelling, high-quality visual content and interactions with followers, to create a memorable and positive experience for its customers. This study emphasizes the importance of digital branding for the success of companies in the current competitive environment, highlighting the relevance of well-designed presence and engagement strategies on social networks, especially on popular platforms such as Instagram.

Keywords: E-branding, iFood, Instagram, Strategies.

RESUMO

Este estudo examina as estratégias de e-branding empregadas pela iFood, através de um estudo de caso das suas postagens no Instagram durante o período de 05 de janeiro a 16 de abril de 2024. Utilizando a metodologia qualitativa e a análise de conteúdo, investiga-se as principais características do branding da iFood na plataforma. Os resultados revelam que a iFood adota uma

¹ Received on 20/02/2025. Accepted on 24/03/2025. DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20284077

² UNIPÊ Centro Universitário de João Pessoa. saraiionara@gmail.com

³ UNIPÊ Centro Universitário de João Pessoa. raissasantosb@hotmail.com

⁴ Vinicius_torres_98@hotmail.com

RELISE

abordagem estratégica no Instagram, visando construir uma marca forte e relevante para o seu público-alvo. A empresa utiliza diversos recursos, como *storytelling*, conteúdo visual de alta qualidade e interações com os seguidores, para criar uma experiência memorável e positiva para os seus clientes. Este estudo enfatiza a importância do branding digital para o sucesso das empresas no ambiente competitivo atual, destacando a relevância de estratégias bem elaboradas de presença e engajamento nas redes sociais, especialmente em plataformas populares como o Instagram.

Palavras-Chaves: e-branding, iFood, Instagram, estratégias.

INTRODUCTIONO

The impactful presence of technology in contemporary society is reflected both in consumption patterns and sales strategies. The growing ubiquity of the internet in daily communication makes the migration of organizations to the online environment a natural evolution, given the centrality of this platform for social interaction (VAZ, 2010). Given this change in consumer behavior, companies have not only been compelled to adapt to social networks but also to use them as a crucial tool for promotion and even for commercial transactions.

The way the consumer is reached and influenced represents a crucial point, where the harmonization of interests and a strong presence on social media become increasingly significant differentiators among brands. In this context, communication and information technologies play a fundamental role in global integration through a digital communication system that simultaneously embraces cultural diversity and personalizes experiences according to individual identities (JUNQUEIRA, 2011).

According to Kotler (2010) and other researchers, the accelerated dissemination of internet-driven content has become a vital factor for both consumers and organizations. The speed of access to information has made the sales and consumption scenario increasingly competitive, requiring marketing to become more efficient. The new marketing paradigm is clearly centered on social media and our ability to reach and engage individuals.

RELISE

113

As technology continues to transform people's lives, organizational marketing needed to evolve to keep up with this process and get closer to their target audience (HIGINO et. al., 2017; SILVA et. al., 2019; CAETANO et. al., 2016). In this context, iFood stands out as a significant object of study in this article, considering its prominence in the current scenario.

iFood is a food delivery platform that has revolutionized the market in various ways, simplifying the process of ordering food, making it quick and convenient at any local restaurant or food establishment. The variety of food offered by the platform, together with the convenience of food delivery and the real-time tracking system, has transformed the user experience. In addition, iFood has stimulated the growth of small businesses, boosting their sales and visibility.

According to a 2020 survey by the Economic Research Institute Foundation (Fipe), iFood moved around 31.9 billion in the country, equivalent to 0.43% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Moreover, between January 2015 and December 2019, iFood generated an average of 10,472 jobs per month, and by the year 2020, 730,000 jobs had been created, representing 0.72% of the Brazilian population. These data highlight the importance of iFood in job creation and the country's economic scenario.

The choice to investigate the development of iFood's branding through its Instagram posts is based on several fundamental reasons. First, iFood is a prominent company on both national and international levels, especially in the food delivery sector, making it a relevant object of study to understand branding strategies in a highly competitive environment. Additionally, Instagram is one of the main social media platforms used by iFood to communicate with its consumers and build its brand image, thus serving as a strategic channel to analyze the impact of its posts on brand strengthening.

Given this context, and considering the modernization of marketing, this article's main objective is to understand the development of iFood's branding through its Instagram posts. To achieve this goal, the following specific objectives will be explored: understanding how digital marketing impacts iFood, exploring the company's business branding, and comprehending Instagram's impact on the business as a whole.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Digital marketing

Digital Marketing has become an indispensable tool for companies seeking to build and strengthen their brands in the online environment. Unlike traditional marketing, which relies on conventional media such as television, radio, and print, digital marketing uses online platforms and digital tools to reach and engage the target audience in a more focused and efficient manner.

In the contemporary commercial landscape, Digital Marketing becomes fundamental as it enables the construction of a well-positioned brand in the market. Furthermore, it enhances customer relationships, increasing loyalty and consequently contributing to sales growth. Based on Kotler (2010), we can affirm that marketing comprises a social process in which individuals and groups satisfy their needs and desires through the creation, offering, and free negotiation of valuable products and services with others.

As the world evolves technologically, marketing also adapts to this environment. Thus, Digital Marketing is not a replacement for traditional marketing; on the contrary, it is a valuable extension that offers greater reach, more accessible costs, and a more precise segmentation of the target audience. Both can coexist complementarily, playing fundamental roles at different stages of interaction between company and consumer.

RELISE

At the initial stage, traditional marketing plays a crucial role in creating awareness and generating interest in the brand. On the other hand, digital marketing assumes a primary role in promoting concrete actions, strengthening brand advocacy, and providing measurable results. This integrated approach, combining traditional and digital strategies, allows companies to reach a broader, more engaged audience that is more likely to become loyal customers (Kotler et al., 2017).

E-commerce, which means electronic commerce, is a fundamental strategy within digital marketing, widely adopted today. Its importance is notable in the geographic expansion of companies, providing greater visibility and convenience for customers. Additionally, e-commerce offers benefits such as the use of access reports, which provide valuable insights to improve products and optimize the user experience on the website.

Albertin (2004, p. 15) defines electronic commerce as "the execution of the entire value chain of business processes in an electronic environment, through the intensive application of communication and information technologies, meeting business objectives." This concept highlights the complete integration of business processes in a digital environment, driven by the efficient use of communication and information technologies.

O'Brien (2004, p. 244) highlights three basic categories of e-commerce applications:

Business-to-Consumer (B2C) e-commerce: In this modality, companies seek to create attractive electronic marketplaces to attract and sell products and services directly to consumers. Business-to-Business (B2B) e-commerce: This involves the operation of electronic markets and direct connections between companies, facilitating commercial transactions between them. Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C) e-commerce: In this model, online auctions stand out, such as those on eBay, where consumers and companies can buy and sell among themselves through an auction process on a dedicated website (O'Brien, 2004, p. 244).

RELISE

116

These categories illustrate the diversity of applications and opportunities offered by e-commerce, which has become an essential pillar for the growth and competitiveness of companies in the digital context. Thus, we define marketing as the set of actions, strategies, and knowledge that results in a science, a study of current markets to promote consumer satisfaction and desires for a product.

Furthermore, based on the research conducted for this study, marketing can also be defined as a social process where individuals and groups obtain their needs through the creation, offering, and free negotiation of valuable goods, products, or services with others, thereby adapting to consumer needs.

Buyer satisfaction after making a purchase depends on the performance of the offer in relation to their expectations; therefore, if their expectations are not met, they will be dissatisfied, and if the product pleases the customer, they will be satisfied. In this context, digital marketing is aimed at significantly increasing the demand for a particular product through social media and electronic channels, adding value by standing out from the competition and also aiming for profits for companies (Kotler, 2017).

Branding in businesses

Branding in Portuguese means "marca" (brand), and it involves building a memorable and positive experience, establishing a solid and meaningful connection with consumers. Thus, its importance in a company goes far beyond the quality of its services and products. According to Kotler (2010), branding should be based on five fundamental principles: consistency, clarity, continuity, visibility, and authenticity.

Consistency is the main principle, as the brand must consistently reflect what the product or service offers. Clarity is crucial so that customers can easily understand the purpose and values of the brand. Continuity involves keeping the brand present and secure in the minds of consumers over time. Visibility is

RELISE

117

essential to boost the brand and keep it relevant in customers' perception. Finally, authenticity seeks to create a unique standard that is practiced by all members of the company, consolidating the brand's identity in a genuine way.

Branding encompasses a set of actions, positioning, values, and processes aimed at adding value and winning an audience through the brand's visual identity and the culture it represents. According to Aaker (2015), the brand vision model is a structural framework for developing a unique and differentiated vision of the brand compared to others, across various dimensions.

This practice involves creating powerful forms of communication that convey the image desired by the brand to the consumer and other strategic audiences. As highlighted by Hiller (2014) in his book *Branding: The Art of Building Brands*, branding is the construction of an image through values, commitments, and credibility, considering that consumers are influenced by cultural, social, and emotional factors when making purchasing decisions.

Instagram

Instagram is a widely used social media platform that allows the sharing of photos and videos with the primary goal of promoting something or oneself. This social network plays a fundamental role in the relationship between brand and consumer. It is often associated with influencers who have a large number of followers, providing broad positive exposure that can result in increased sales.

Instagram is an inexhaustible source of information, enabling the monitoring of people or companies relevant to specific areas of interest. As highlighted by Rosa, Casagrande, and Spinelli (2017), studying the relationships between individuals, groups, and organizations in the purchasing process without considering digital media is a mistake, since social networks are seen as a constantly growing market.

RELISE

118

Thus, Instagram not only facilitates communication and interaction between brands and consumers but also offers opportunities for building relationships, sharing valuable information, and growing digital marketing strategies.

One example is the reality show Big Brother Brasil (BBB), broadcast by Globo, which has been gaining massive viewership and significant engagement on social media. One of the official sponsors of the program is IFood Brasil (figure 1), which takes advantage of the show's enormous audience and the Instagram digital platform, one of the largest impact networks for brands, to spark consumer desire and generate significant impact on sales.

Figure 1 – Feed screenshot

Source – Instagram of Ifood Brasil (2024)

However, as the cited authors highlight, talking about consumption on the internet is not sufficient to fully understand how this phenomenon occurs on social media, nor what factors influence it. Studies conducted have proposed models that facilitate the understanding of consumer motivations in the virtual universe.

RELISE

Figure 2 – Feed screenshot

Source – Instagram of Ifood Brasil

Ifood Brasil represents a significant share of the Brazilian economy, moving 0.53% of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), according to data from FIPE (2024) apud iFood (2024). With the evolution of the current scenario, phone calls to food establishments have been replaced by a simple click on digital platforms. In this context, Instagram, through its partnership and promotion on the reality show, has been used as an effective sales tool, attracting the target audience and contributing to a significant increase in sales.

According to Philip Kotler (2010), currently, the internet offers one of the most exciting and challenging opportunities for professional service companies, allowing them to offer high-quality services to their clients. E-commerce and the internet provide increasing possibilities for customer service and enhancing sales strategies.

METHODOLOGY

Through the theoretical foundation, it is essential to establish a methodology that enables a detailed understanding of the e-branding of the company iFood, aligned with the proposed objectives. Thus, as highlighted by Gil (1987), the development of a research project requires the clear formulation of

RELISE

120

the problem, precise objectives, and a robust plan for data collection and analysis.

Following this context, the methodologies used in the present article include applied and descriptive research. Applied research aims to investigate and understand iFood's e-branding through the practical analysis of its Instagram posts. This approach allows practical problems to lead to the discovery of scientific principles, highlighting the interaction between theory and practice (GIL, 1987).

In turn, the descriptive methodology will be employed to expand the bibliographic context and support the development of iFood's digital branding, according to Köche (1997). Descriptive research seeks to characterize factors associated with the success of the study, providing a comprehensive view of the phenomenon under study.

The qualitative approach will also be adopted in this study with the goal of understanding and analyzing posts on the Instagram platform. This will enable a deeper understanding of the branding strategies employed by iFood in the digital environment, contributing to the consolidation of its brand in the market. This methodology aligns with the perspective of Kirk and Miller (1986), who highlight the importance of close observation to strengthen existing theory and generate valuable insights.

The objective is to conduct a case study, as defined by Yin (2014), which consists of an empirical investigation of a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, using multiple sources of evidence. This approach, together with the theoretical foundation, is suitable for analyzing branding on social media, allowing a comprehensive understanding of the strategies used by iFood, their results, and impact on the target audience.

Based on the analyses carried out on the posts made by iFood on the Instagram digital platform, it is important to emphasize that the data used in this

RELISE

are publicly available, as they are accessible on an internet profile open to any platform user.

The content analyzed in this study focuses on posts published between 01/05/2024 and 04/16/2024. Posts from the feed, stories, and videos in the Reels of the official iFood account were collected. This comprehensive approach will allow a detailed analysis of the communication and branding strategies used by the company throughout this period, offering valuable insights into its presence and interaction on the digital platform.

The analysis of posts will be conducted through non-participant observation, allowing content evaluation without the need for direct interaction, such as liking, commenting, or sharing. Additionally, Instagram's search tool will be used to filter and search for posts by hashtags, keywords, and other relevant criteria. This methodological approach will provide a comprehensive understanding of the communication and branding strategies adopted by iFood in its digital presence without interfering with the natural dynamics of user interactions with the content.

The data collection procedure adopted for this study will be conducted in three well-defined stages. Initially, the analysis period will be delimited, starting with iFood's campaign on the television program Big Brother Brasil (BBB) and extending until the program's conclusion, as previously mentioned. Once this period is defined, relevant posts will be manually collected using Instagram's search tools and available social media analysis tools.

Subsequently, the data obtained from the posts will be organized in a spreadsheet, following specific criteria for efficient categorization. This spreadsheet will contain crucial information for analysis, such as the publication date of each post, the type of post (feed, stories, reels), the theme addressed, the hashtags used, and the number of likes, comments, and shares of each post. This systematic organization of data will allow a thorough and structured analysis

RELISE

of the branding strategies employed by iFood in its Instagram presence during the studied period.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the analysis of three segments was conducted: Stories, Feed, and Reels videos of iFood on Instagram. This approach allowed a detailed understanding of the communication and branding strategies employed by the company in different content formats on the social platform. By examining Stories, Feed, and Reels videos, patterns of engagement, creativity, and interactivity were identified, contributing to a broad view of the impact of iFood's digital marketing strategies on the target audience.

Stories postings

Human interaction plays a crucial role in the dynamics of the relationship between supplier and consumer within the digital environment (YANAZE et al., 2022). In the context of digital marketing, this interaction becomes even more significant, as it allows brands to connect more closely and authentically with their target audience.

According to Alves (2021) apud Braz (2023), Stories was introduced by Instagram in 2016 as a response to the success of Snapchat, which adopted a similar logic. Although initially perceived as less important in terms of engagement, the format quickly gained popularity among users, becoming a common practice to share everyday moments in Instagram Stories (BRAZ, 2023).

Based on the cited authors, this tool became a way to keep followers updated about the user's life, acting almost like a digital "diary" that establishes a closer connection between the publisher and their followers.

Considering this concept, an analysis was conducted on the stories published by iFood during the study period, aiming to identify smart engagement strategies and how the interaction between the company and the consumer

RELISE

occurred. It was observed that at strategic times, known as activity "peaks," the company posted polls, questions to followers, and used interactive stickers, as exemplified in figure 3.

Besides the usual question boxes, polls were included with snack options that would make the user "abandon" the leader's challenge or interactive stickers with sweets that the user would save from elimination. These three Options - polls, questions to followers, and the use of interactive stickers - were especially effective in stimulating user participation, promoting meaningful interactions with the brand and consequently contributing to increased engagement and revenue.

Figure 3 – Screenshot of the highlight BBB 24

Source – Instagram of Ifood Brasil

Another relevant point observed was the frequency of stories and their contextualization with specific events. The content was directed according to the day of the week and what would happen in BBB. For example, on Mondays, stories related to the "game of discord" were posted, while on Sundays, the focus was on which snack would best match an elimination.

It was observed that this strategy of alignment with relevant events not only increased the relevance of the posts but also generated greater interest and interaction from the company's target audience. According to Yanaze et al. (2022), Stories can be considered the most popular form of sharing temporary

RELISE

content; however, they tend to generate more transient interaction compared to Feed posts, whether photos or videos, especially when it comes to sharing and saving publications.

It is worth noting that these aspects were carefully examined to understand the impact of this form of communication on the company's target audience, resulting in valuable insights to improve future engagement and branding strategies.

Feed postings

The Feed, by definition, comprises posts that remain permanently on the user's profile, which can be deleted or archived according to preference. These posts may include photos, videos, or even carousels, which are sequences of up to 10 photos (BRAZ, 2022). Practically speaking, the Feed can be compared to a virtual showcase where the user can highlight relevant and impactful content for their followers.

The analysis of the posts on iFood's Instagram feed covered several crucial aspects for understanding the brand's branding strategy. Initially, the consistency of the company's visual identity was observed, ensuring that the posts maintained a cohesive aesthetic aligned with the brand's values and style. Additionally, the variety of content shared was a highlight, ranging from recipes and promotions to event coverage related to the program.

A significant element observed in these posts was iFood's ability to make smart correlations with program events or the participants themselves. For example, in figure 4, the satin cap represented Giovanna Pitel and the visor represented Fernanda Bande, with the post accompanied by the caption "Tag that duo who will keep enjoying the party with you." This creative approach not only generated interest and engagement but also promoted the brand subtly and effectively.

RELISE

125

Figure 4 – Screenshot of iFood feed related to BBB 24

Source – Instagram of Ifood Brasil

Another analyzed aspect was the strategic use of hashtags and location tags. The hashtags #iFoodNoBBB24 and #BBB24 were widely used, significantly contributing to the increased reach and visibility of the posts. The first, with more than 500 posts, was exclusive to iFood, while the second, with over 1.1 million posts, was used by participants, viewers, and other brands.

This strategy not only strengthened follower engagement but also expanded the brand's exposure to a broader and more diverse audience, resulting in greater awareness and recognition of iFood within the context of the program and beyond.

Reels vídeos

Reels videos are defined as dynamic content due to their publication format, which ranges from 15 to 90 seconds (BRAZ, 2022). In this context, the videos produced by iFood were meticulously analyzed in terms of creativity, originality, and relevance to the target audience of this research.

According to Yanaze et al. (2022), videos hold considerable weight compared to other forms of publication, demonstrating their greater relevance to

RELISE

126

the audience. This preference can be attributed to the dynamic and interactive nature of videos, which enable an emotional connection and deeper engagement with followers.

When observing the reels videos on iFood's digital platform, not only their entertainment value is notable but also their alignment with current trends, which ensured an effective connection with followers. Aspects such as video duration, music choice, and visual effects were carefully evaluated in the analysis, as well as followers' responses through views, shares, and comments.

This detailed analysis of the different types of content published by iFood on Instagram provided a comprehensive understanding of the e-branding strategies adopted by the company on the platform. As with stories and feed posts, reels videos aimed to attract and promote interaction with customers.

It is important to highlight that reels videos received a considerably higher number of views, shares, and comments, indicating their effectiveness in engaging the audience and promoting the brand dynamically and impactfully (YANAZE et al., 2022).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The focus of this research was the analysis of the e-branding strategies adopted by iFood and their influence on increasing brand engagement. During this analysis, valuable practices were identified that can be applied by other companies seeking to strengthen their digital presence and expand involvement with their target audience.

One of the main highlights was the use of interactive content, such as polls, questions to followers, and interactive stickers, especially in Stories posts. This approach stimulated user participation and promoted more meaningful interactions with the brand.

RELISE

127

Another relevant point, in agreement with the previously cited authors, was the consistency in the brand's visual identity on iFood's Instagram feed. Maintaining a cohesive visual aesthetic aligned with the company's values can generate recognition and familiarity among followers, contributing to the strengthening of the brand in the digital environment.

Leveraging current events and trends was also a strategy explored by iFood, particularly in relation to the Big Brother Brasil (BBB) program. This practice allows companies to connect more relevantly and timely with their audience, generating greater interest and interaction. iFood's successful practices on Instagram offer valuable insights for other organizations looking to improve their digital strategy. By adopting approaches such as interactive content, visual consistency, strategic hashtag use, creativity in videos, and leveraging events, companies can strengthen their online presence and achieve more effective results in the digital environment.

It is important to highlight that the objective of this work was fully achieved by analyzing the importance of digital e-branding for companies, emphasizing how the strategies adopted by iFood can serve as a model for other organizations. However, it is also important to note some limitations of the study, such as the exclusive focus on iFood and the analysis of a specific period, which may limit the generalization of the results to other companies or different time frames.

The contributions of this study are diverse, including the identification of effective digital e-branding practices, the correlation between theory and practice through the analysis of iFood's data, and the suggestion of strategies that other companies can apply to strengthen their digital presence and increase engagement with their target audience. These contributions are relevant to the field of digital marketing and strategic management, providing valuable insights for professionals and researchers interested in the topic.

RELISE

REFERENCES

AAKER, David. **On branding: 20 princípios que decidem o sucesso das marcas**. Bookman Editora, 2015.

ALBERTIN, A. L. **Comércio eletrônico: modelo, aspectos e contribuições da sua aplicação**. 2ª ed. São Paulo: Atlas, 2004.

BRAZ, Igor Danilo dos Santos. **Conexão e engajamento com os consumidores a partir do Instagram: o caso da empresa VR Veículos Recife**. Recife: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, 2023.

CAETANO, L. M. *et. al.* **Marketing digital: conceitos, estratégias e ferramentas**. São Paulo: Pearson, 2016.

HIGINO, T. C. *et. al.* **Marketing digital: teoria e prática na era da informação**. São Paulo: Atlas, 2017.

HILLER, Marcos. **Branding: a arte de construir marcas**. Editora Trevisan, 2014.
GIL, A. C. **Como elaborar projetos de pesquisa**. São Paulo: Atlas, 1987.

Institucional iFood. iFood movimentada 0,53% do PIB brasileiro, segundo a Fipe. **Estudos e Pesquisas, Notícias**. 2024, 02 jan. Disponível em: <https://institucional.ifood.com.br/estudos-e-pesquisas/ifood-movimentada-053-do-pib-brasileiro-segundo-a-fipe/>. Último acesso dia 13 mai 2024.

JUNQUEIRA, V. **A sociedade da informação: cultura e comunicação na era digital**. São Paulo: Editora Loyola, 2011.

RELISE

129

KIRK, J., & MILLER, M. L. Reliability and validity in qualitative research. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications, 1986.

KÖCHE, J. C. **Metodologia de pesquisa**. Petrópolis: Vozes, 1997.

KOTLER, P. **Marketing de resultados**: como obter o que você deseja do seu marketing. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2010.

KOTLER, P., KARTAJAYA, H. SETIAWAN, I. (2017). **Marketing 4.0**: Mudança do Tradicional para o Digital. Coimbra, Portugal: Conjuntura Actual Editora: 2017. Trad. Pedro Elói Duarte. (218 páginas). Vol.14 nº 27 | 2019.

O'BRIEN, James A. **Sistema de Informação e as decisões gerenciais na era da internet**. 2 ed. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2004.

ROSA, Renato de O.; CASAGRANDA, Yasmin G.; SPINELLI, Fernando E. A importância do marketing digital utilizando a influência do comportamento do consumidor. **Revista de tecnologia aplicada (RTA)** v.6, n.2, mai-ago 2017, p.28-39 ISSN: 2237-3713. (EBSCO)

SILVA, A. M. *et. al.* **Marketing digital**: estratégias e ferramentas para o sucesso online. Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier, 2019.

VAZ, C. E. **Marketing 3.0**: a comunicação no mundo digital. Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier, 2010.

RELISE

130

YANAZE, Mitsuru Higuchi; et al. **Marketing Digital: conceitos e práticas**. São Paulo: SaraivaUni, 2022.

YIN, Roberto. K. **Estudo de caso: pesquisa qualitativa em ciências sociais**. Porto Alegre: Bookman Editora, 2014.